

Neutrosophic Hypercompositional Structures defined by Binary Relations

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Abstract: The objective of this paper is to study *neutrosophic* hypercompositional structures $H(I)_\tau$ arising from the hypercompositions derived from the binary relations τ on a *neutrosophic* set $H(I)$. We give the characterizations of τ that make $H(I)_\tau$

hypergroupoids, quasihypergroups, semihypergroups, *neutrosophic* hypergroupoids, *neutrosophic* quasihypergroups, *neutrosophic* semihypergroups and *neutrosophic* hypergroups.

Keywords: hypergroup, neutrosophic hypergroup, binary relations.

1 Introduction

The concept of hyperstructure together with the concept of hypergroup was introduced by F. Marty at the 8th Congress of Scandinavian Mathematicians held in 1934. A comprehensive review of the concept can be found in [5, 6, 12]. The concept of neutrosophy was introduced by F. Smarandache in 1995 and the concept of *neutrosophic* algebraic structures was introduced by F. Smarandache and W.B. Vasantha Kandasamy in 2006. A comprehensive review of *neutrosophy* and *neutrosophic* algebraic structures can be found in [1, 2, 3, 4, 15, 24, 25].

One of the techniques of constructing hypergroupoids, quasi hypergroups, semihypergroups and hypergroups is to endow a nonempty set H with a hypercomposition derived from the binary relation ρ on H that give rise to a hypercompositional structure H_ρ . In this paper, we consider binary relations τ on a neutrosophic set $H(I)$ that define hypercompositional structures $H(I)_\tau$. Hypercompositions in $H(I)$ considered in this paper are in the sense of Rosenberg [22], Massouros and Tsitouras [16, 17], Corsini [8, 9], and De Salvo and Lo Maro [13, 14]. We give the characterizations of τ that make $H(I)_\tau$ hypergroupoids, quasihypergroups, semihypergroups, *neutrosophic* hypergroupoids, *neutrosophic* quasihypergroups, *neutrosophic* semihypergroups, and *neutrosophic* hypergroups.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. Let H be a non-empty set, and

$\circ : H \times H \rightarrow P^*(H)$ be a hyperoperation.

- (1) The couple (H, \circ) is called a hypergroupoid. For any two non-empty subsets A and B of H and $x \in H$, we define

$$A \circ B = \bigcup_{a \in A, b \in B} a \circ b, A \circ x = A \circ \{x\} \text{ and}$$

$$x \circ B = \{x\} \circ B$$

- (2) A hypergroupoid (H, \circ) is called a semihypergroup if for all a, b, c of H we have $(a \circ b) \circ c = a \circ (b \circ c)$, which means that

$$\bigcup_{u \in a \circ b} u \circ c = \bigcup_{v \in b \circ c} a \circ v.$$

A hypergroupoid (H, \circ) is called a quasihypergroup if for all a of H we have $a \circ H = H \circ a = H$. This condition is also called the reproduction axiom.

- (3) A hypergroupoid (H, \circ) which is both a semihypergroup and a quasihypergroup is called a hypergroup.

Definition 2.2. Let $(G, *)$ be any group and let

$$G(I) = \langle G \cup I \rangle. \text{ The couple } (G(I), *) \text{ is called a}$$

neutrosophic group generated by G and I under the binary

operation $*$. The indeterminacy factor I is such that

$I * I = I$. If $*$ is ordinary multiplication, then

$IastI * \dots * I = I^n = I$ and if $*$ is ordinary addition, then

$I * I * I * \dots * I = nI$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

If $a * b = b * a$ for all $a, b \in G(I)$, we say that $G(I)$ is commutative. Otherwise, $G(I)$ is called a non-commutative neutrosophic group.

Theorem 2.3. [24] Let $G(I)$ be a neutrosophic group. Then,

- (1) $G(I)$ in general is not a group;
- (2) $G(I)$ always contain a group.

Example 1. [3] Let $G(I) = \{e, a, b, c, I, aI, bI, cI\}$ be a set, where $a^2 = b^2 = c^2 = e$, $bc = cb = a$, $ac = ca = b$, $ab = ba = c$. Then $(G(I), \cdot)$ is a commutative neutrosophic group.

Definition 2.4. [4] Let (H, \circ) be any hypergroup and let $H(I) = \langle H \cup I \rangle = \{(a, bI) : a, b \in H\}$. The couple $(H(I), \circ)$ is called a neutrosophic hypergroup generated by H and I under the hyperoperation \circ .

For all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$, the composition of elements of $H(I)$ is defined by

$$(a, bI) \circ (c, dI) = \{(x, yI) : x \in a \circ c, y \in a \circ d \cup b \circ c \cup b \circ d\}.$$

Example 2. [4] Let $H(I) = \{a, b, (a, aI), (a, bI), (b, aI), (b, bI)\}$ be a set and let \circ be a hyperoperation on H defined in the table below.

\circ	a	b	(a,aI)	(a,bI)	(b,aI)	(b,bI)
a	a	b	(a,aI)	(a,bI)	(b,aI)	(b,bI)
b	b	a	(b,bI)	(b,aI)	(a,bI)	(a,aI)
		b		(b,bI)	(b,bI)	(a,bI)
						(b,aI)
						(b,bI)
(a,aI)	(a,aI)	(b,bI)	(a,aI)	(a,aI)	(b,aI)	(b,bI)
				(b,bI)	(b,bI)	
(a,bI)	(a,bI)	(b,aI)	(a,aI)	(a,aI)	(b,aI)	(b,aI)
		(b,bI)	(a,bI)	(a,bI)	(b,bI)	(b,bI)
(b,aI)	(b,aI)	(b,bI)	(b,aI)	(b,aI)	(a,aI)	(a,aI)
		(a,bI)	(b,bI)	(b,bI)	(a,bI)	(a,bI)
					(b,aI)	(b,aI)
					(b,bI)	(b,bI)
(b,bI)	(b,bI)	(a,aI)	(b,bI)	(b,aI)	(a,aI)	(a,aI)
		(a,bI)		(b,bI)	(a,bI)	(a,bI)
		(b,aI)			(b,aI)	(b,aI)
		(b,bI)			(b,bI)	(b,bI)

Then $(H(I), \circ)$ is a neutrosophic hypergroup.

Definition 2.5. Let H be a nonempty set and let ρ be a binary relation on H .

- (1) $\rho \circ \rho = \rho^2 = \{(x, y) : (x, z), (z, y) \in \rho, \text{ for some } z \in H\}$.
- (2) An element $x \in H$ is called an outer element of ρ if $(z, x) \notin \rho^2$ for some $z \in H$. Otherwise, x is called an inner element.
- (3) The domain of ρ is the set $D(\rho) = \{x \in H : (x, z) \in \rho, \text{ for some } z \in H\}$.
- (4) The range of ρ is the set

$$R(\rho) = \{x \in H : (z, x) \in \rho, \text{ for some } z \in H\}.$$

In [22], Rosenberg introduced in H the hypercomposition

$$\begin{aligned} x \circ x &= \{z \in H : (x, z) \in \rho\} \text{ and} \\ x \circ y &= x \circ x \cup y \circ y \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

and proved the following:

Proposition 2.6. [22] $H_\rho = (H, \circ)$ is a hypergroupoid if and only if $H = D(\rho)$.

Proposition 2.7. [22] H_ρ is a quasihypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $H = R(\rho)$.

Proposition 2.8. [22] H_ρ is a semihypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $\rho \subseteq \rho^2$.
- (3) $(a, x) \in \rho^2$ implies that $(a, x) \in \rho$ whenever x is an outer element of ρ .

Proposition 2.9. [22] H_ρ is a hypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $H = R(\rho)$.
- (3) $\rho \subseteq \rho^2$.
- (4) $(a, x) \in \rho^2$ implies that $(a, x) \in \rho$ whenever x is an outer element of ρ .

In [17], Massouros and Tsitouras noted that whenever x is an outer element of ρ , then it can be deduced from condition (2) and (3) (conditions (3) and (4)) of Proposition 2.8 (Proposition 2.9) that $(a, x) \in \rho$ if and only if $(a, x) \in \rho^2$ for some $a \in H_\rho$. Hence, they restated Propositions 2.8 and 2.9 in the following equivalent forms:

Proposition 2.10. [17] H_ρ is a semihypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $(a, x) \in \rho^2$ if and only if $(a, x) \in \rho$ for all $a \in H$ whenever x is an outer element of ρ .

Proposition 2.11. [17] H_ρ is a semihypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $H = R(\rho)$.
- (3) $(a, x) \in \rho^2$ if and only if $(a, x) \in \rho$ for all

$a \in H$ whenever x is an outer element of ρ .

If H is a nonempty set and ρ is a binary on H, Massouros and Tsitouras [17] defined hypercomposition \bullet on H as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x \bullet x &= \{z \in H : (z, x) \in \rho\} \text{ and} \\ x \bullet y &= x \bullet x \cup y \bullet y \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

and stated that:

Proposition 2.12. [17] If ρ is symmetric, then the hypercompositional structures (H, \circ) and (H, \bullet) coincide.

Following Rosenberg's terminology in [22], Massouros and Tsitouras established the following:

Definition 2.13. [17]

- (1) For $(a, b) \in \rho$, a is called a predecessor of b and b a successor of a.
- (2) An element x of H is called a predecessor outer element of ρ if $(x, z) \notin \rho^2$ for some $z \in H$.

Using hypercomposition \bullet , Massouros and Tsitouras established the following:

Proposition 2.14. [17] $H_\rho = (H, \bullet)$ is hypergroupoid if and only if $H = R(\rho)$.

Proposition 2.15. [17] $H_\rho = (H, \bullet)$ is quasihypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $H = R(\rho)$.

Proposition 2.16. [17] $H_\rho = (H, \bullet)$ is semihypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = R(\rho)$.
- (2) $(x, y) \in \rho^2$ if and only if $(x, y) \in \rho$ for all $y \in H$ whenever x is a predecessor outer element of ρ .

Proposition 2.17. [17] $H_\rho = (H, \bullet)$ is hypergroup if and only if

- (1) $H = D(\rho)$.
- (2) $H = R(\rho)$.
- (3) $(x, y) \in \rho^2$ if and only if $(x, y) \in \rho$ for all $y \in H$ whenever x is a predecessor outer element of ρ .

If H is a nonempty set and ρ is a binary relation on H, Corsini [8, 9] introduced in H the hypercomposition:

$$x * y = \{z \in H : (x, z) \in \rho \text{ and}$$

$$(z, y) \in \rho \text{ for some } z \in H\}. \tag{3}$$

It is clear that $(H, *)$ is a partial hypergroupoid and it is a hypergroupoid if for each pair of elements $x, y \in H$, there exists $z \in H$ such that $(x, z) \in \rho$ and $(z, y) \in \rho$. Equivalently, $(H, *)$ is a hypergroupoid if and only if $\rho^2 = H^2$.

If H_ρ is the hypercompositional structure defined by equation (3), Massouros and Tsitouras [16] proved the following:

Proposition 2.18. [16] H_ρ is a quasihypergroup if and only if $(x, y) \in \rho$ for all $x, y \in H_\rho$.

Lemma 2.19. [16] If H_ρ is a semihypergroup and $(z, z) \notin \rho$ for some $z \in H_\rho$, then $(s, z) \in \rho$ implies that $(z, s) \notin \rho$.

Corrolary 2.20. [16] If H_ρ is a semihypergroup and ρ is not reflexive, then ρ is not symmetric.

Lemma 2.21. If H_ρ is a semihypergroup then ρ is reflexive.

Proposition 2.22. [16] H_ρ is a semihypergroup if and only if $(x, y) \in \rho$ for all $x, y \in H_\rho$.

Definition 2.23. A hyperoperation $*$ defined through ρ is said to be a total hypercomposition if and only if $(x, y) \in \rho$ for all $x, y \in H_\rho$. In other words, $*$ is said to be a total hypercomposition if $x * y = H_\rho$ for all $x, y \in H_\rho$.

Remark 1. If a hypercompositional structure H_ρ is endowed with the total hypercomposition $*$, then $(H_\rho, *)$ is a hypergroup.

Theorem 2.24. [16] The only semihypergroup and the only quasihypergroup defined by the binary relation ρ is the total hypergroup.

If H is a nonempty set and ρ is a binary relation on H ,

De Salvo and Lo Faro [13, 14] introduced in H the hypercomposition:

$$x \diamond y = \{z \in H : (x, z) \in \rho, (z, y) \in \rho \text{ for some } z \in H\}.$$

They characterized the relations ρ which give quasihypergroups, semihypergroups and hypergroups.

3 Neutrosophic Hypercompositional Structures

3.1 Neutrosophic Hypercompositional Structures of Rosenberg Type

Let τ be a binary relation on $H(I)$ and let $\rho = \tau|_H$. For all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$, define hypercomposition on $H(I)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (a, bI) \circ (c, dI) &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : x \in a \circ a, \\ & \quad y \in a \circ a \cup b \circ b\} \\ &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : (a, x) \in \rho, \\ & \quad (a, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, y) \in \rho\}. \end{aligned}$$

(5)

$$\begin{aligned} (a, bI) \circ (c, dI) &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : x \in a \circ a \cup c \circ c, \\ & \quad y \in a \circ a \cup b \circ b \cup c \circ c \cup d \circ d\} \\ &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : (a, x) \in \rho, \\ & \quad \text{or } (c, x) \in \rho, (a, y) \in \rho \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or } (b, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (c, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (d, y) \in \rho\}. \tag{6}$$

Let $H(I)_\tau = (H(I), \circ)$ be a hypercompositional structure arising from the hypercomposition defined by equation (6).

Proposition 3.1.1. $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a hypergroupoid. Then $H = D(\rho)$ and from equation (6) we have $(a, bI) \circ (c, dI) \subseteq H(I)_\tau$ for all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$. Hence $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid. The converse is obvious.

Proposition 3.1.2. $H(I)_\tau$ is a quasihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a quasihypergroup.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a quasihypergroup. Then $H = D(\rho) = R(\rho)$. Let $(x, yI) \in (a, bI) \circ (c, dI)$ for an arbitrary $(c, dI) \in H(I)$. Then

$$(a, bI) \circ H(I)_\tau = \bigcup \{(a, bI) \circ (c, dI)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \bigcup \{ (x, yI) \in H(I) : (a, x) \in \rho, \\
 &\quad \text{or } (c, x) \in \rho, (a, y) \in \rho \\
 &\text{or } (b, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (c, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (d, y) \in \rho \}. \\
 &= H(I)_\tau
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, it can be shown that

$$H(I)_\tau \circ (a, bI) = H(I)_\tau \text{ for all } (a, bI) \in H(I).$$

Hence $(H(I)_\tau, \circ)$ is a quasihypergroup. The converse is obvious.

Lemma 3.1.1. If ρ is not reflexive, then $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \circ (a, bI)$ for all $(a, bI) \in H(I)$.

Proof. Suppose that ρ is not reflexive and suppose that $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \circ (a, bI)$ for all $(a, bI) \in H(I)$. Assuming that $(a, b) \in \rho$, we have from equation (5):

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a, bI) \circ (a, bI) &= \{ (a, bI) \in H(I) : (a, a) \in \rho, \\
 &\quad (a, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, b) \in \rho \} \\
 &= \emptyset
 \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction. Hence $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \circ (a, bI)$.

Proposition 3.1.3. $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup if ρ is reflexive and symmetric.

Proof. Suppose that ρ is reflexive and symmetric. Let $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$ be arbitrary and let $(x, a) \in \rho$, $(x, b) \in \rho$ and $(y, a) \in \rho$. Then $(b, aI) \in (a, bI) \circ ((b, aI) \circ (a, bI))$ implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a, bI) \circ ((b, aI) \circ (a, bI)) &= \{ (b, aI) \in H(I) : (a, b) \in \rho \\
 &\text{or } (x, b) \in \rho, (a, a) \in \rho, (b, a) \in \rho \text{ or } \\
 &\quad (x, a) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, a) \in \rho \} \\
 &= ((a, bI) \circ (b, aI)) \circ (a, bI).
 \end{aligned}$$

This shows that

$(b, aI) \in ((a, bI) \circ (b, aI)) \circ (a, bI)$. Since (a, bI) and (b, aI) are arbitrary, it follows that $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup.

The following results are immediate from the hypercomposition defined by equation (6):

Proposition 3.1.4. (1) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

(2) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic semihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a semihypergroup.

(3) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic hypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroup.

3.2 Neutrosophic Hypercompositional Structures of Massouros and Tsitouras Type

Let τ be a binary relation on $H(I)$ and let $\rho = \tau|_H$. For all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$, define hypercomposition on $H(I)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a, bI) \bullet (a, bI) &= \{ (x, yI) : x \in a \bullet a, \\
 &\quad y \in a \bullet a \cup b \bullet b \} \\
 &= \{ (x, yI) : (x, a) \in \rho, \\
 &\quad (y, a) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, b) \in \rho \} \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a, bI) \bullet (c, dI) &= \{ (x, yI) : x \in a \bullet a \cup c \bullet c, \\
 &\quad y \in a \bullet a \cup b \bullet b \cup c \bullet c \cup d \bullet d \} \\
 &= \{ (x, yI) : (x, a) \in \rho, \\
 &\quad \text{or } (x, c) \in \rho, (y, a) \in \rho \text{ or } \\
 &\quad (y, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, c) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, d) \in \rho \} \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$(H(I)_\tau, \bullet)$ be a hypercompositional structure arising from the hypercomposition defined by equation (8).

Proposition 3.2.1. If ρ is symmetric, then hypercompositional structure $(H(I)_\tau, \bullet)$ coincide with hypercompositional structure $(H(I)_\tau, \circ)$.

Proof. This follows directly from equations (6) and (8).

Proposition 3.2.2. $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a hypergroupoid. Then $H = R(\rho)$ and from equation (8) we have $(a, bI) \bullet (c, dI) \subseteq H(I)_\tau$ for all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$. Hence $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid. The converse is obvious.

Proposition 3.2.3. $H(I)_\tau$ is a quasihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a quasihypergroup.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a quasihypergroup. Then $H = D(\rho) = R(\rho)$. Let $(x, yI) \in (a, bI) \bullet (c, dI)$ for an arbitrary $(c, dI) \in H(I)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a, bI) \bullet H(I)_\tau &= \bigcup \{ (a, bI) \bullet (c, dI) \} \\
 &= \bigcup \{ (x, yI) \in H(I) : (x, a) \in \rho \\
 &\quad \text{or } (x, c) \in \rho, (y, a) \in \rho \text{ or } \\
 &\quad (y, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, c) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, d) \in \rho \} \\
 &= H(I)_\tau
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, it can be shown that

$$H(I)_\tau \bullet (a, bI) = H(I)_\tau \text{ for all } (a, bI) \in H(I).$$

Hence $H(I)_\tau$ is a quasihypergroup. The converse is obvious.

Lemma 3.2.1. If ρ is not reflexive, then $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \bullet (a, bI)$ for all $(a, bI) \in H(I)$.

Proof. The same as the proof of Lemma 3.1.1.

Proposition 3.2.4. $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup if ρ is reflexive and symmetric.

Proof. This follows from Proposition 3.1.3 and Proposition 3.2.1.

Proposition 3.2.5. (1) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

(2) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic semihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a semihypergroup.

(3) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic hypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroup.

3.3 Neutrosophic Hypercompositional Structures of Corsini Type

Let τ be a binary relation on $H(I)$ and let $\rho = \tau|_H$. For all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$, define hypercomposition on $H(I)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (a, bI) * (c, dI) &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : x \in a * a, \\ &\quad y \in a * d \cup b * c \cup b * d\} \\ &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : (a, x) \in \rho, \\ &\quad \text{and } (x, c) \in \rho, [(a, y) \in \rho \\ &\quad \text{and } (y, d) \in \rho] \text{ or } [(b, y) \in \rho \text{ and } (y, c) \in \rho] \\ &\quad \text{or } [(b, y) \in \rho \text{ and } (y, d) \in \rho]\}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Let $H(I)_\tau = (H(I), *)$ be a hypercompositional structure arising from the hypercomposition defined by equation (9).

Proposition 3.3.1. $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a hypergroupoid. Then $H^2 = \rho^2$. Since $(a, c), (a, d), (b, c), (b, d) \in \rho^2$ from equation (9), it follows that $(a, bI) * (c, dI) \subseteq H(I)_\tau$ for all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$. Hence $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid. The converse is obvious.

Proposition 3.3.2. $H(I)_\tau$ is a quasihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a quasihypergroup.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a quasihypergroup. Then $(x, y) \in \rho$ for all $x, y \in H$. Let $(x, yI) \in (a, bI) * (c, dI)$ for an arbitrary $(c, dI) \in H(I)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (a, bI) * H(I)_\tau &= \bigcup \{(a, bI) * (c, dI)\} \\ &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : (a, x) \in \rho, \\ &\quad \text{and } (x, c) \in \rho, [(a, y) \in \rho \\ &\quad \text{and } (y, d) \in \rho] \text{ or } [(b, y) \in \rho \text{ and } (y, c) \in \rho] \\ &\quad \text{or } [(b, y) \in \rho \text{ and } (y, d) \in \rho]\}. \\ &= H(I)_\tau \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, it can be shown that

$H(I)_\tau * (a, bI) = H(I)_\tau$ for all $(a, bI) \in H(I)$. Hence $H(I)_\tau$ is a quasihypergroup. The converse is obvious.

Proposition 3.3.3. $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic quasihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a quasihypergroup.

Proof. Follows directly from equation (9).

Lemma 3.3.1. If ρ is not reflexive and symmetric, then

- (1) $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) * (a, bI)$
for all $(a, bI) \in H(I)$.
- (2) $(b, aI) \notin (a, bI) * (a, bI)$
for all $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.
- (3) $(a, aI) \notin (a, bI) * (a, bI)$
for all $(a, aI), (a, bI) \in H(I)$.
- (4) $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) * (a, bI)$
for all $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.
- (5) $(b, aI) \notin (a, bI) * (b, aI)$
for all $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.
- (6) $(a, aI) \notin (a, bI) * (b, aI)$
for all $(a, aI), (a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.

Proof. (1) Suppose that ρ is not reflexive and symmetric and suppose that $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) * (a, bI)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (a, bI) * (a, bI) &= \{(a, bI) \in H(I) : (a, a) \in \rho, \\ &\quad (b, b) \in \rho \text{ or } [(a, b) \in \rho \text{ and } \\ &\quad (b, b) \in \rho] \text{ or } [(b, b) \in \rho \text{ and } (a, b) \in \rho]\} \\ &= \emptyset \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction. Hence $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) * (a, bI)$. Using similar argument, (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6) can be established.

Proposition 3.3.4. $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup if ρ is reflexive and symmetric.

Proof. Suppose that ρ is reflexive and symmetric. Let $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$ be arbitrary and let $(x, a) \in \rho$, $(x, b) \in \rho$, $(y, b) \in \rho$ and $(b, a) \in \rho$. Then $(a, bI) \in (a, bI) * ((b, aI) * (a, bI))$ implies that $(a, bI) * ((b, aI) * (a, bI)) = \{(a, bI) \in H(I) : (x, a) \in \rho \text{ and } (a, a) \in \rho, [(x, b) \in \rho \text{ and } (b, b) \in \rho] \text{ or } [(y, a) \in \rho \text{ and } (b, a) \in \rho] \text{ or } [(y, b) \in \rho \text{ and } (b, b) \in \rho]\} = ((a, bI) * (b, aI)) * (a, bI)$.

This shows that $(b, aI) \in ((a, bI) * (b, aI)) * (a, bI)$. Since (a, bI) and (b, aI) are arbitrary, it follows that $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup.

Corollary 3.3.1. $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a semihypergroup.

Proposition 3.3.5. If any pair of elements of H_ρ does not belong to ρ , then $H(I)_\tau$ is not a semihypergroup.

3.1 Neutrosophic Hypercompositional Structures of De Salvo and Lo Faro Type

Let τ be a binary relation on $H(I)$ and let $\rho = \tau|_H$. For all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$, define hypercomposition on $H(I)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (a, bI) \diamond (c, dI) &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : x \in a \diamond c, \\ &\quad y \in a \diamond d \cup b \diamond c \cup b \diamond d\} \\ &= \{(x, yI) \in H(I) : (a, x) \in \rho, \\ &\quad \text{or } (x, c) \in \rho, (a, y) \in \rho \\ &\quad \text{or } (b, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, c) \in \rho \text{ or } (y, d) \in \rho\}. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Let $H(I)_\tau = (H(I), \diamond)$ be a hypercompositional structure arising from the hypercomposition defined by equation (10).

Proposition 3.4.1. If ρ is symmetric, then hypercompositional structures $(H(I), \diamond)$, $(H(I), \circ)$ and $(H(I), \bullet)$ coincide.

Proof. Follows directly from equations (6), (8) and (10).

Proposition 3.4.2. $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

Proof. Suppose that H_ρ is a hypergroupoid. Then $H=D(\rho)$ or $H=R(\rho)$ and from equation (10) we have $(a, bI) \diamond (c, dI) \subseteq H(I)_\tau$ for all $(a, bI), (c, dI) \in H(I)$. Hence $H(I)_\tau$ is a hypergroupoid. The converse is obvious.

Proposition 3.4.3. $H(I)_\tau$ is a quasihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a quasihypergroup.

Proof. The same as the proof of Proposition 3.2.3.

Lemma 3.4.1. If ρ is not reflexive and symmetric, then

- (1) $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (a, bI)$
for all $(a, bI) \in H(I)$.
- (2) $(b, aI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (a, bI)$
for all $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.
- (3) $(a, aI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (a, bI)$
for all $(a, aI), (a, bI) \in H(I)$.
- (4) $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (a, bI)$
for all $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.
- (5) $(b, aI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (b, aI)$
for all $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.
- (6) $(a, aI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (b, aI)$
for all $(a, aI), (a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$.

Proof. (1) Suppose that ρ is not reflexive and symmetric and suppose that $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (a, bI)$. Then

$$(a, bI) \diamond (a, bI) = \{(a, bI) \in H(I) : (a, a) \in \rho, (a, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, a) \in \rho\}$$

$$= \emptyset$$

a contradiction. Hence $(a, bI) \notin (a, bI) \diamond (a, bI)$. Using similar argument, (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6) can be established.

Proposition 3.4.4. $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup if ρ is reflexive and symmetric.

Proof. Suppose that ρ is reflexive and symmetric. Let $(a, bI), (b, aI) \in H(I)$ be arbitrary and let $(a, x) \in \rho, (b, x) \in \rho, (b, y) \in \rho$ and $(a, b) \in \rho$. Then $(a, bI) \in (a, bI) \diamond ((b, aI) \diamond (a, bI))$ implies that $(a, bI) \diamond ((b, aI) \diamond (a, bI)) = \{(a, bI) \in H(I) : (a, a) \in \rho \text{ or } (a, x) \in \rho, (a, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, y) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, b) \in \rho \text{ or } (b, x) \in \rho\} = ((a, bI) \diamond (b, aI)) \diamond (a, bI)$.

This shows that $(a, bI) \in ((a, bI) \diamond (b, aI)) \diamond (a, bI)$. Since (a, bI) and (b, aI) are arbitrary, it follows that $H(I)_\tau$ is a semihypergroup.

The following results are immediate from the hypercomposition defined by equation (10):

Proposition 3.4.5. (1) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic hypergroupoid if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroupoid.

(2) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic semihypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a semihypergroup.

(3) $H(I)_\tau$ is a neutrosophic hypergroup if and only if H_ρ is a hypergroup.

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